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Rethinking Video Games in Critical Discourse: Re-Visiting Intersections of the ICT Hypertext and Artistic Consumption

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Abstract

This paper set out to investigate the critical environment of videogames not merely as technology but also as art. Departing from the premise that functionalist readings of videogames say little about the evolution of the technology in its critical environment, it applied a de Certeaurian critical paradigm and came up with certain findings. As a digital technology, the videogame has been subject to new definitional considerations; it is a new agency of production, consumption and distribution of digital goods and services, sharing, communication, interaction, and socialization.

Beyond technology, the videogame has become a new experience of artistic consumption that prioritizes not only individual participation, but also posting of video comments, blog responses, video postings as well as conversations and texts. The videogame is an artistic way of finding new identities and freedoms that strengthens the concept of consumption not as the active use of a product, service or brand, but as the individualization, passivity and alienation of experience.

Keywords

Video games, functionalism,, intersection, sharing, art, communication, interaction, player, flanerie, participation

1.0 Introduction

The current tendency in the scholarship on videogames consists of prioritizing the focus on their functionalism in various segments and activities of contemporary society. For example, a number of studies explore how videogames make expressive statements about the world; they investigate the singular persuasive power of videogames in the light of their computational qualities (Wright and Bogost. 2007, Bogost 2008, Juul 2011, Salen Tekinbaş and Zimmerman. 2003, Frasca, 2013). The studies handle the cultural history of digital gameplay in terms of player behaviour, and this includes practices like cheating, and the relationship of this behaviour to the game industry. The experiences of players of digital games as they challenge the concept of a single correct way to play are also investigated (e.g. Consalvo 2009, Newman 2008. Juul 2010, Galloway 2006, Mäyrä 2008, Kline, Dyer-Witthof, and De Peuter 2003, Juul 2011).

The stream of scholarship shows that some devotees to the digital technology with a knowledge of culture, art, and a real love of gaming compare the aesthetic and economic impacts of videogames on society (e.g. Herz 1997, Wolf 2001, Juul 2001, Berger 2017).

Other studies approach videogames by considering how interactive, immersive entertainment, or videogame playing, has emerged as an important entertainment and educational medium. The intention behind this set of studies is to place educational researchers in a position to benefit by developing more grounded theories about them, as more development initiatives and research proliferate (e.g. Squire, 2006, Gee, 2003, Squire 2008, Shaffer 2005, Steinkuehler 2006, Squire and Mingfong 2007, Barab et al. 2005, Squire 2011, Gee 2007). Scholars examine the lifestyles of male and female school goers in order to totalize the amount of time and money spent playing videogames, the social environment that prevails during videogame sessions, and their viewing of TV violence. The aim here is to find out the relationships between these students and their interactive environments (e.g. Cooper and Mackie 1986, Lin and Lepper 1987, Schutte et al. 1988, Fling et al. 1992, Anderson and Ford. 1986, Silvern and Williamson 1987). Teenagers of fourteen years have been

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administered with questionnaires in order to evaluate the extent to which their needs and gratifications were met by TV

viewing and videogames. In this approach, basic demographic characteristics are considered as well as the home TV viewing environments in order to discern the relationship between TV viewing and videogame playing (e.g. Wigand, Borstelmann and Boster 1986, Griffiths 1993, Colwell, Grady and Rhaiti 1995, Gibb et al. 1983, Phillips et al. 1995, McClure and Mears 1984, Griffiths 1991, Egli and Meyers 1984). Some studies approach videogames in the light of how they equip children with high technology, to enable them to overcome technophobia, which is prevalent among many adults. The hope here is that in due time, videogames may as well enable users to

eliminate gender imbalance in the employment of IT, given that males have the tendency to be more avid IT users (e.g. Griffiths 2003, Pearson and Bailey 2007, Bailey and Pearson – 2007, Pearson and Bailey 2008, Sayfullina 2017).

This paper departs from this functionalist model of analyzing videogames, which assumes that the practice of digital technology takes place in a vacuum of *unfalsifiability* and *ahistoricism*, by rethinking the videogame as an open-ended cyberspace that is in an active, fluid and complicated contact with its changing political economy and discursive environments. It therefore scrutinizes the videogame in its new and post-historicizing contexts as a discourse of undecidability in order to show how the technology is both impacted by that environment and how it is fighting to impose itself on that environment not in its narrow sense as technology in corporate establishments but in its wider sense as art with a high adaptability capacity in the agency of user-generated content, interactivity and participation.

2.0 Method and materials

This paper draws insights from Michel de Certeau's theory which declares that players of technology are not simply grazing on the simulacra ration that the technological system distributes to each person. His theoretical paradigm also observes that the system's expansion does not provide consumers with any place where they can show what they do or make of the system's products (Michel de Certeau 1984).

3.0 Critical definitional issues

A videogame is digital gameplay, an expressive culture developed through the agency of intertextual interpretation and collaborative performance. Rockstar's game design can be helpful to further illuminate videogames as a 'liminal site' of playing along where immersion enhancing realism blends with immersion disrupting citation and parody and the player is not quite in that world, yet he is of it, not a tourist nor a local of it and is acting naturally whereas he has to come off with new knowledge from it (Miller 2012). A player of videogames attempts to move CJ via his episodic travails. The CJ is not created by the player, who may or may not identify with him. A storyteller may tell a tale, but it does not necessarily mean that he identifies with the main character of the tale. Just as an actress may act a film but it does not necessarily follow that she identifies with the film's protagonist. Videogames draw their content and modes of expression from both traditional folklore and contemporary public narratives but different players of videogames come with various portfolios of interpretation to construct their own normative practices and vernacular cultures around them (Hill 1997). Today, the context of videogames has changed as they are adopted worldwide with different interpretive traditions and aesthetics of participatory culture. For example, there are cut-scene transcriptions, maps, screenshots, discussion forums, and mission guides that are disseminated globally.

However, contemporary mass media and other accounts are denying this rich diversity behind the expressive videogame culture of collaborative performance and are rather prioritizing its subjection to the 'bad influence' theory of assumptions of totalizing effects on players. As an ICT hypertext, videogames impact on the cultural values and beliefs of consumers. So, they are re-presented in public discourse as a programming code that governs the comportment of their inherently acquiescent gaming avatars. As a result, the videogame

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metanarrative has been susceptible to new interpretive discourses as an agency of violence and is associated with the active performance of criminal behaviour, sexual perversion, brainwashing, long hours of immersion in repetitive game tasks, and so forth.

The functionalist metanarrative of the videogame has also been decoded into new political stakes. For example, during the June 14, 2006 hearing of the House Sub-Committee on Trade, Commerce and Consumer Protection, Congressman Joseph Pitts declared as follows (Ryan M. 2013:6): “ it is safe to say that a wealthy kid from the suburbs can play *Grand Theft Auto* or other games without turning to a life of crime, but a poor kid who lives in a neighbourhood where people really do steal cars or deal drugs or shoot cops might not be so fortunate” Although the videogame is authored, designed, published, licenced and played by different actors, it is considered as a technology that can only be ‘experienced’, a mere representation, or a digital animation and not a game *per se*.

4. Production, consumption and distribution of digital media goods and services

Videogames are a digital mode of communication and from that sense, they are just like a computer, a cell phone or a television set. However, as a new digital medium, they are not so much new in the sense of a spectacular break from the past. Rather, they are ‘new’ in the sense that they are a new way of constructing questions of production, consumption and distribution of digital medium. They are new ways of comprehending relationships between media and humans. Videogames animate four major types of relationships that entail production, consumption and distribution. These relationships are sharing, communicating, socializing and interacting.

Videogames are a practice informed by what may be referred to as consumer ‘ways of seeing.’ However, this consideration often leads to the negative evaluation that videogames are not about interactivity, but are rather about a form of pleasure that aims to pacify leisure. Nevertheless, this objection stands in contrast to the negative assessment that videogames generate violence or construct a culture of isolation and a glorification of new freedoms found via digital virtual consumption. It is also possible to put forth the point from here that videogamers enact a performance of consumer scripts and do so in dramatic environments that have the potential to ‘re-enchant’ consumer experience. However, this strengthening view of videogames opens up to the assaulting observation that, in the reproduction of consumer acts, consumer spectacles like videogames alienate and depoliticize the consumer.

4.1 Sharing.

Videogames have transformed how digital media users share the products of their media labour. Sharing is now a very personal and sociological action that is carried out through websites, blogs, videos and vlogs. Unlike the old way of sharing, the new way now is that it is mediatized. Consequently, this new form of sharing is not restricted to power brokers and media elites in talk shows, but is extended to any ordinary user who desires to produce content for sharing and is connected to the internet. This new relationship is based on consumer-generated content and can take the form of video comments and blogs. Video is now the most important consumer-generated content. It is now very popular because of the availability of the digital camera and the user-friendly editing software that facilitates the explosion of the labour of digital ‘artists’ so that the fruits of their work can be offered online through websites dealing with consumer-generated content. YouTube remains the most important website on consumer-generated content and its historicism is connected to the advent of the video as a major text of the digital age.

4.2. Communication

It is through communication that we can comprehend the culture and it is only through means of culture that we can understand communication. All individual or institutional media works are acts of communication. However, digital media such as videogames have changed the old conception that we used to have about communication. Videogames now communicate by integrating the new idea of mobility. Consequently, there is a major shift in the relationship between users and the spaces where people live and communicate through. Cell phones have created new ways of accelerating mobility in the sense that users can now transport their media

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environment to any place that they visit. The cellphone has transformed the very idea of communication as an experience of mobility, unlike the television or the cinema which stationed the viewer before a large or small screen in a room. Other communicators or mobile devices are also substituting the cellphone by offering other functions that enable users to listen, watch and talk to a large variety of media texts. The composite range of these functions is moulding how we think about communication as a digital media function. Cellphones now facilitate the functions of talking, listening and writing. Television is also available on the iPhone and it is now possible to enjoy consumer-generated content in the user's computer. But cellphone communication is now being encoded with specific meanings that are connected to ideology and culture.

4.3. Socialization

In the past, people always socialized by deploying culture. Today, videogames are functioning to create new ways of constructing socialization. They construct new patterns of formation of communities that parallel patterns in the offline world but also develop in different directions, thereby mobilizing new communities and group identities. These group identities are affiliated to politics, self-help, religion, fanaticism, gossip and so forth. The socialization of the media can now be textualized through video. Unlike in the past when the production of text was stressed through traditional methods, today, the agents of socialization emphasize mobilization. As soon as videogame comments are posted, the attention, engagement and response of the community they are introduced into, is invited. Community membership is then circumscribed, determined and assessed in terms of how each community member is self-involved and the responses that they create online. A number of social media websites such as MySpace and Facebook present with textual content that is authored by users, who are involved in socialization.

4.4. Interactivity

People have always interacted in the past. Students interacted in class. Business people interacted in restaurants. Spectators interacted in a football stadium. However, when it comes to the videogame, the concept of media technology interaction was taken to new and different levels. Interaction now involved new forms of comportment such as shouting at the technology - seen at the same level of the human as an actor - because, for example, it generates a poor signal at a given time, enjoying a digitally sculpted landscape in a videogame machine, etc. thus, interactivity has shifted from the old practices of inert passivity of observers of narratives to a new form of interactivity where the posting of video comments, blog responses, video postings as well as conversations and texts, are at the centre. The interactive experience of the videogame goes beyond a mere act of watching and includes a playing action of the game narrative effectively. In the experience of playing the videogame, the gamer is not outside but rather inside the action. In this case, the original text of the game is recast and reworked through thousands of players who take pleasure in revisiting the original game narrative. This experience of re-textualizing is critical for comprehending how an experiential reading or an ethnographic investigation into videogames may be articulated (Kavoori 2010: 4).

Discussion

In the hypothetical continuum intersecting the videogame and its critical environment, the videogame becomes very trendy because it is a virtual environment that reproduces consumer ways of perception. The creation of gazes, namely, spatial, panoptic and temporal, present as both the environment of trade design and as an art of game design. The two types of designs are embedded in the objects and spaces of the videogame. They invite the player to explore their visual stimulus, colour, shapes, and novelties. This exploration, in turn, triggers new desires and new reflections on possibilities of outcomes. The numerous outcome possibilities prohibit any kind of loitering on any particular videogame site, and this constitutes a facilitating mechanism for effective consumption of the game. As a space of insights for retail planning, videogames present opportunities for designers to consider new options that can seduce consumers. Thus, the spaces of retail constitute one important way of experiencing the capitalist economy. The videogame signifies a new way of enjoying spaces of manufactured spectacle in which drama, colour and gaze connive to appropriate the reader's attention.

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The *Sims* with its spatial, neighbourhood gaze, the *Tetris* with its temporal gaze, and the *Dawn of the Dead* with its panoptic gaze, actually represent the shopping experience in real life. In *Gran Turismo*, the player actually strolls through a car showroom displaying physical features and architectures associated with that sector of marketing. The games present shopping simulations without the kinds of physical restrictions (time, space, etc) found in real shop settings.

Although videogames may be seen as an enhanced version of the technology, they are not simply a digital technology but an art form generated with or influenced by it. It has its genres and practitioners. Videogame art exhibits a variety of techniques and styles but forms a distinct movement with shared aesthetic preoccupations. For most people, videogames are the first point of contact with computers, they are a popular and shared cultural capital. They are recognizable to novices but have the potential to take connotations beyond their original meanings, content and context. They are deployed by artists as a source of material inspiration as they create their own games in due course of time. As art, they have triggered research programmes in academia and have inspired books and conferences. Currently, whether from the viewpoint of narratology or from a perspective of ludology, videogames are considered in the light of their mechanics, that is, the factors that contribute to the gameplay or game narrative instead of from the angle of their game aesthetics or qualities that can be appreciated on their own terms or in their own right (Andy and Grethe, eds. 2007). Thus, the suggested perspective is to move away from game design or craft to game aesthetics or art. The challenge now is how to move the videogame metanarrative from a misunderstood and obscure perspective to a creative, mass-socializing and lucrative discourse of artistic hobby with its own language, culture, conventions and mass-market.

The power of survivability of the videogame against media denigration is in its ability to mutate its forms as its peripheral technologies are upgraded and change. The technology is not a static medium and any attempt to understand it as such with traditional models of analysis will fail in the end to disintegrate it. As an artistic form, videogames embed a huge cultural activity that engages with industry. They exhibit the qualities and markings of artistic works. The campaigns to degrade videogames are ineffective because the players are enjoying the game, and they enjoy it because it is an art. The artistic form is produced by digital creators and it is dependent on cyberspace technologies that are being innovated all the time and have the potential to disrupt medium. When the videogame is played, it brings enjoyment to the creator and the player because it can be experienced in terms of never starting it, or never completing it; it can be won, lost or experienced in other ways. It can be a representative of a play, novel, story, history, dance, film, etc and therefore can incarnate the qualities of these art forms. Whatever difference exists between these art forms and the videogame is insignificant and even irrelevant for players.

The assault on videogames, preoccupied with concerns over their promotion of violence, conceals other social aspects of social analysis of the digital media. By focusing excessively on violence, critics become blind to new issues such as what the videogame is saying about the contemporary practices of consumer society. Thus, beyond violence, videogames re-enchant the consumer via new forms of the spectacle and by reconstructing the shopping script and the consumer gaze, which risks dehumanizing consumers. The shopping culture can be seen as a way of comprehending the videogame as a digital video culture. Beyond consumption as a utilitarian and rationalist possession of products and services, it can also be an experience that is founded on the imagination and the gaze. There is a relationship existing between the playing of videogames and recreational shopping. This relationship is founded on the 'scopic regimes' of the shopper. This fact has the potential to open up new insights for and against videogames. Recreational shopping is an aesthetic experience that deploys environmental resources to stimulate imagination and construct a pleasurable dream-space. Through the 'tourist gaze' or the consumption of touristic sites, and the 'scopic regime' of shopping, the emphasis is on the experience than on the image, the stress is on the given that consumers gaze at things rather than on objects being looked at. The experience is one of the videogames moving through a dream-space with the player settling on particular objects from time to time in order to contemplate their meaning. Thus, the player who plays several videogames experiences a thrilling form of entertaining shopping (Ibid: 62).

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The designers of videogames have tapped into the culturally desirable experiences that players afford from their virtual *flanerie*. Consequently, it has grown to become an artistic way of finding new identities and freedoms that strengthens the concept of consumption not as the active use of a product, service or brand, but as the individualization, passivity and alienation of experience. Videogames are an escape route from the Taylorism culture of political economy that mechanizes labour and consumption as rigid, stages of social evolution. Although it may be argued that videogames are an attempt at instituting new forms of commodification (Kline, Dyer-Witheford and De Peuter 2003, Urry 2002)

Concluding remarks

How does one explain the fact that despite media attempts and political campaigns to denigrate videogames like *Grand Theft Auto* and *The Sims*, signified as a glorification of consumer lifestyles, the cyberspace technology continues to thrive in a twenty billion dollar industry? This paper has attempted to answer that question by showing that the videogame technology has interacted with the political economy environment of denigration but, from this confrontation, an artistic form has emerged that in its own right that is popularized through the agency of the player. The videogame player is now seduced by this spectacular form of art which is actually virtualization and fetishization of the economic product or service, but this time as art. This is the *flanerie* product that lounges and the imagination of the player are also challenged to stroll and gaze and then derive pleasure from this process as a reward that trickles down as corporate profit but a remuneration that is artistic, personalized and therefore greater than whatever economic benefits the corporate world derives in his eyes. As a result, any attempt to criticize capitalist consumption styles through the interactions in *Dawn of the Dead* cannot be effective because, beyond the pleasurable gains derived from the videogame, interactivity in it intersects with a hugely passive experience of 'consumption'. Videogames are not simplistically a capitalist consumer culture, they are also a highly thrilling and enchanting experience of art with a huge potential for renewable flexibility, diversity, variation and novelty. This indeed is the ingredients with which its artistic flavor and texture are enmeshed.

The videogame is an artistic re-enchantment of the capitalist culture of shopping. Shopping as an activity dealing with products and services has now been transformed into an experience drawing its resource from the artistic thrill, a marketable *flanerie* that is flexible through the romantic gaze of virtual scenes, the panoptic gaze of the machine, the occasional glance at a familiar site, and so forth. This paper has been able to emerge with these findings because it shifted its analytical method from a functionalist to a discursive, tacit and critical reading of videogames.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Sketch Bio

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